

Effects of pre-slaughter stress on poultry meat and its control measures

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Abstract

The quality of poultry meat is impacted by pre-slaughter factors. The eating quality of meat, including pH, color, thawing loss, cooking loss, and toughness, is negatively impacted by pre-slaughter stress such as loading, unloading and etc. These quality changes have a significant negative impact on profits because they decrease meat yield, shelf life, and consumer acceptability. Only animals that are physiologically healthy should be slaughtered to avoid any weight loss and other quality changes. A number of pre-slaughter handling conditions may be carefully handled and quality loss can be managed along with poultry welfare.

Introduction

Pre-slaughter phase in the production process of poultry meat has important implications for animal welfare. Various potential stressors like, noise, unfamiliar environments vibration, and thermal variations throughout the transport, handling, feed and water withdrawal, high density in crates, and lairage time could predispose damage and even death, possibly more so when flocks are in a poor health condition or immunocompromised. On the other hand, it also affects the quality of meat produced. The incidence of pale, soft, and exudative (PSE)-like chicken meat is high worldwide. The incidence of PSE (pale, soft and exudative) pork meat is directly influenced by pre-slaughter handling of animals, compromising meat quality and leading to economic losses for industry. Considering management, the main extrinsic stress factors are: the pre-slaughter rest time in lairage, the total fasting time and at farm and the transport time. PSE-like chicken meat also affects the sensory qualities of fresh meat, which can decrease the consumer's purchasing desire, reduce chicken meat functionality, and decrease product yield, leading to extensive economic losses for the poultry processing industry.

This meat defect has been of increasing concern to processors and researchers in the poultry processing industry about factor, which contribute toward pre- slaughter stress.

Some of the major factors contributing to pre slaughter stress in Poultry

Heat stress before slaughter

Heat stress is a major concern for poultry, particularly within the hot regions of the world because of the resulting poor growth performance, immunosuppression, and high mortality. Poultry exposed to heat stress before slaughter showed the lowest ultimate pH. This decline in pH is a result of glycolysis and ATP hydrolysis. Exposure to acute heat stress is likely to lead to various metabolic changes in poultry meat.

Physical contact, Crating and transport

Crating causes a rise in plasma corticosterone levels in broilers (Kannan and Mench, 1996). The duration of crating (Kannan and Mench, 1996) and the method of crating (Duncan, 1989) can also affect the stress response shown by the bird. Although catching, crating, and loading are the procedures that are most possibly to cause physical injuries, transportation has conjointly been reported to be stressful to broilers. Further, fear levels in birds were mostly determined by transportation and not just by catching and loading. Ehinger (1977) found that broiler meat tenderness and water holding capacity were reduced after 2 h of transportation but improved after 4 h of transportation and transport stress can influence the color and texture of broiler meat.

Struggle and shackling

Struggle and shackling on the shackle line throughout the processing and hanging operations could induce severe struggling (straightening up, wing flapping and vocalization) on the shackle line (Gregory and Bell, 1987), increase plasma corticosterone and affect muscle peri-mortem metabolism and some meat attributes.

Feed & water withdrawal

Feed is generally withdrawn for several hours before catching to reduce the danger of carcass contamination. Total feed withdrawal times of 8 to 10 h before slaughter are recommended, although in practice longer periods sometimes occur. Feed withdrawal affects a lot of metabolic processes. Feed deprivation causes a shift from constructive metabolism to destructive metabolism, from lipogenesis to lipolysis, and a reduced metabolic rate. Feed withdrawal induces behavioral and physiological responses, indicating that broilers probably suffer from stress. An increase in corticosterone concentrations has been shown in broilers after a feed and water withdrawal of 24 h. Feed withdrawal

before slaughter allows emptying of the digestive system and reduces the likelihood of faecal contamination during processing. The preslaughter and eviscerated weights were decreased as the length of feed withdrawal period increased.

Seasons

During the early summer season, the turkey industry reports substantial losses in yield due to poor water-holding capacity, poor texture and pale colour. Heat stress has been associated with increased mortality and researchers found that chronic heat stress has been shown to result in a 20% reduction in growth rate in fast-growing strains of poultry. Heat stress in summer has long been recognized as one of the prominent environmental elements influencing meat quality. Stress as caused by either excitation or increased temperature prior to slaughter reportedly produces redder muscle.

Lairage time

Chickens may be temporarily held in lairage before slaughtering to get over from transport stress. However, an improper holding period can be a significant factor in lowering meat quality. Lairage periods longer than 2 or 4 h alter the metabolism, cause hyperglycemia, hypercalcemia, hyperlactatemia, hyperkalemia, hyponatremia, acidosis, severe dehydration, and modify the physical parameters in chicken meat. Sometimes, a continuous processing line in slaughterhouses involves a extended lairage time to maintain the animal stock before slaughtering.

Control measures to prevent Quality Loss

Poultry meat quality is potentially affected by management techniques (feed withdrawal, transportation and lairage), weather (temperature and season), genetics, stunning, the ability of the birds to respond to the atmosphere, dietary feed additives, common stressors and every variables that may interact, affecting in the production cycle which is not only important in respect of quality but also important as welfare of the birds. Poultry industry peoples will obtain good quality meat by better understanding of these management techniques.

Lairage Time

At high temperatures (above 22 °C), an increase in the lairage time reduced the mortality rates, being more pronounced in the critical (25 – 28 °C) and lethal intervals (above 29 °C). In relation to lairage time, the reduction in rate of mortality was more pronounced in the intervals up to 1 hour of waiting. So that, the lairage time recommended for broilers during heat stress conditions is over 1 hour, and the greater intervals are more desirable for poultry welfare subjected to pre-slaughter operations.

Lactic acid supplement

Proliferation of pathogenic bacteria is due to decrease in crop lactic acid and increased pH which can be minimizing with incorporation of lactic acid in the drinking water during pre-transport.

Stunning

Stunning renders animals insensible throughout slaughtering procedures. several methods can be used for stunning birds like chemical, mechanical and electrical. Electrical water bath stunning is that the most typical approach of stunning of birds in industrial poultry process plants, which shows that higher current frequency (≥ 480 Hz) results increased post-mortem pH scale declining rate and improved meat quality as compared to the lower frequency (≤ 350 Hz). Carcass damage can be reduced due to the elimination of muscular contracture; pain is eliminated; and rigor mortis is accelerated. Other possible advantages are improved working conditions within the hanging area and reduction in pre-slaughter stress if birds are killed by extended gas exposure period before shackling.

Glucose supplementation

A negative post-slaughter impact of the poultry having withdrawal of food –water and having been transported for long hours may end up in reduced slaughter yields and negative influences on meat texture and meat pH scale. Such animals are often in a negative energy balance state, blood glucose concentration decreases, the non-esterified fatty acid (NEFA) level increases, and glycogen stores decreases. Saccharose supplementation throughout feed withdrawal appears to have a measurable impact on shrinkage, lightness of liver and redness of thigh meat colour in broilers.

Conclusion

The meat quality of poultry is affected by conditions like feed management, transportation, lairage holding, temperature, genetics of birds, handling during stunning and during slaughtering. Careful handling of such pre-slaughter factors will not only improve the meat quality but also covers the welfare point. By having a better understanding of these management techniques, poultry industry workers would be able to obtain meat of high quality.

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